

DISEASES RISK ASSESSMENT ASSOCIATED TO THE MOST RELEVANT INFECTIOUS AND PARASITIC DISEASES IN SEABREAM AND SEABASS FARMING SYSTEMS IN EUROPE

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Introduction:

Prevention is one of the most relevant aspects to provide efficient tools for improving health management in aquaculture. However, establishing useful guidelines for this purpose is not an easy task since the development of diseases in fish are usually multifactorial. The combination and impact of different factors, such as the characteristics of the infectious agents and fish host, environmental conditions, geographical parameters, and farming systems amongst others represents the main elements that determine the risk or likelihood to be impacted by a certain disease. The knowledge of these factors allows to establish biosecurity and prophylactic measures to reduce the risks of emergence of pathogens and the susceptibility to infectious diseases. Thus, the aim of this study is to assess the relevance of these factors in order to identify the main risk factors for the most relevant diseases in gilthead seabream and European seabass in Europe

Methods:

The relevance of the different diseases of farmed gilthead seabream and European seabass in the European Mediterranean farms was evaluated after an accurate review of the available literature and discussed amongst a panel of fish health specialists from the e PerformFISH consortium. Once diseases were selected, the risks concerning each disease were also identified by a specialist working team formed by scientists using a HAZOP (Hazard and Operability Study) evaluation system, combined with the information available from technical and scientific literature for each disease, as well as from the personal clinical experience of the members of the working team. After this preliminary internal assessment, each risk factor associated to specific diseases and relevant production phases was scored by a broader panel of experts using DELPHI techniques. Experts had to assess each risk recognized by the team of specialists from 1 to 5, depending on its relevance to face problems with the disease or to avoid them.

Results:

The main diseases of gilthead seabream and European seabass selected by specialist in the Mediterranean Sea were Viral Nervous Necrosis (VNN), Photobacteriosis and disease caused by *Sparicotyle*. The main risks selected by specialists associated to these diseases were grouped in three categories: those related to farm environment (water supply, environmental conditions, epidemiological status of the farm, location...), general management (husbandry procedures, feeding, origin and control of new fish...) and risks associated with the management to avoid a specific disease (efficient protocols to detect pathogens, treatments, vaccination...).

Based on these results, dedicated well-trained personnel and with high awareness of well-established biosafety protocols was considered the most relevant factor to avoid the appearance of VNN in a facility. This recommendation was common to all the production phases. Concerning risks, the supplementation of broodstock with wild fish was the riskiest practice for VNN in broodstock facilities, and the origin of the eggs and juveniles from an external supplier with no specific VNN-health certification were identified as the main risk factors in the other phases of the production system. However,

in the case of ongrowing, the highest score on VNN sanitary risks was related to the location of the cages, considering the farms located in a VNN endemic area and with water temperatures above 25 °C the ones with highest VNN risk. On the other hand, there was an agreement that one of the most beneficial practices to avoid VNN infections in both cages and tanks production systems in ongrowing was the systematic vaccination with VNN commercial vaccines following the manufacturer's recommendations.

Vaccination was also considered the most beneficial practice to avoid Photobacteriosis in ongrowing cages, especially if fry vaccinated with bath and IP booster, in all fish stocks, and using of autologous vaccines instead of commercial vaccines. A rapid action by feeding with medicated feeds immediately after the detection and identification of the outbreak is also considered a good practice to avoid infections in this case. The main risks considered by the experts related to Photobacteriosis are associated to the farm environment, such as the location of the farm in a Photobacteriosis endemic area and/or with frequent or sudden thermal oscillations.

Finally, similar to bacterial disease, the farm environment has an essential role in the appearance of problems with *Sparicotyle*. In this case, to place the farm in a shallow area with weak water currents and/or with a large number of seabream (escapees) around the cages are the main risk factors, but also the management of the farm, if no year-class distribution is applied. A specific management for *Sparicotyle* is strongly recommended to avoid problems with this parasite, for example periodically net changing in several cages and according to *Sparicotyle* infection levels in the farm.

Conclusion:

Taking into account all the considerations and scores by specialist and experts, seems that biosecurity is the best strategy to avoid infectious problems in broodstocks, hatcheries and nurseries, meanwhile, vaccination and management are the keys to reduce the potential impact of the disease in ongrowing stages